

Electrochemically generated Superoxide Initiated Reaction with some Chalcones

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Manuscript received 11 May 1994, revised 7 December 1994, accepted 2 February 1995

During the past two decades, considerable attention has been focused on the chemistry and the reactivity of biologically important superoxide anion¹ which acts as an effective nucleophile², base³, oxidant⁴, reductant⁵ and free radical⁶ depending upon the nature of the organic molecule and presence of other effectors. Rosenthal and Frimer reported⁷ the cleavage of chalcones by the use of KO_2 in 18-crown-6-ether. Recently, cleavage of chalcone by electrogenerated superoxide anion, $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$, in DMF have been reported⁸ from our group. The epoxidation of enones and alkenes have been achieved⁹ by the reaction of electrogenerated $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ (also using KO_2) with above substrates in presence of effectors like acylhalides, carbon acids and metalloporphyrins. It was demonstrated⁹ that $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ itself is not exceptionally reactive in chemical and biological systems. Though, superoxide itself is not so reactive in chemical reaction in aprotic solvents⁹, it is likely that it would be activated by forming more active peroxy species which are generated by the reaction of $\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$ with other suitable substrates. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the reactivity of chalcones with superoxide anion in presence of benzoyl chloride⁹. The results described in this study are different from that reported earlier⁸, carried out in the absence of benzoyl chloride.

cent yield. In all cases traces of benzoic acid was also isolated.

Scheme 1

It is rather difficult to propose a mechanism for the reaction with the present data. Scheme 2, however, attempts to outline a plausible pathway⁸ of dimerisation of chalcones as mediated by superoxide ion. The role of benzoyl chloride is not clearly understood. It probably helps in enhancing the radical anion formation and dimerisation process. The radical anion of substrate generated probably dimerises readily to the product¹¹.

Scheme 2

The chalcones, viz. dibenzylideneacetone (1), benzylideneacetophenone (2), *p*-anisylideneacetophenone (3) were prepared according to the reported method¹⁰. These were reacted with electrochemically *in situ* generated superoxide.

Results and Discussion

The chalcones (1-3) react with *in situ* electrochemically generated superoxide anion at -1.0 V vs SCE in the presence of benzoylchloride in dimethylformamide solution to afford 1,1,2,2-tetrastrylethandiol (1a), 1,2-diphenyldistyrylethandiol (2a) and *p*-anisyl-2,2-dibenzoylethan-1-ol (3a) respectively (Scheme 1) in 60-70 per-

TABLE 1—REACTION OF ELECTROCHEMICALLY GENERATED SUPEROXIDE ANION WITH CHALONES (1–3) IN PRESENCE OF BENZOYL CHLORIDE TO AFFORD COMPOUNDS (1a–3a)*

Compd.	Current (mA)		Electricity passed (Coulomb)	Current efficiency (%)	Product yield (%)	M.p. °C	v_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		m/z
	Initial	Final					OH	C = C	
1	150	10	268	62	1a (65)	205	3 500–2 500	1 620	470 (M ⁺), 452, 324, 77
2	120	08	285	58	2a (60)	175–80	3 520–2 500	1 620	418 (M ⁺), 296, 208, 105, 77
3	145	15	390	46	3a (70)	105	3 550–2 500	1 675	360 (M ⁺), 238, 202, 105

* All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

Experimental

M.p.s. were measured with a Büchi apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer. The quantity of electricity passed was measured using a copper coulometer. DMF was used after drying over molecular sieve (3 Å). Oxygen was dried by passing it through a packed column of anhydrous CaSO₄, NaOH pellets and molecular sieve (3 Å).

In a typical experiment, a solution of tetrabutylammonium bromide (3.22 g, 0.1 mol) in acetonitrile (100 ml) was used as a supporting electrolyte. The cathodic chamber containing the electrolytic solution was pre-electrolysed at -1.9 V (vs SCE) until the background current dropped to about 2 mA. Cyclohexene (2 ml) was added in the anodic chamber to absorb the liberated bromine (cyclohexene is not needed when tetrabutylammonium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte). Catholyte was saturated with oxygen for 30 min. Dibenzylidene acetone (**1**; 0.5 g, 2.1 mmol) and benzoyl chloride (0.5 g; 3.5 mmol) were added to the cathodic chamber [similarly benzylideneacetophenone (**2**; 0.5 g, 2.4 mmol) and benzoyl chloride (0.5 g, 3.5 mmol), anisylideneacetophenone (**3**; 0.5 g, 2.1 mmol) and benzoyl chloride (0.5 g, 3.5 mmol) were also added in separate experiments] and electrolysis was carried out at constant potential of -1.0 V (vs SCE) and the progress of product formation checked by tlc. At the completion of the reaction, appreciable fall in current (Table 1) was observed. After completion of reaction, the catholyte was filtered and the filtrate, after concentration (on rotavapor), was taken in cold water (100 ml), treated with NaHCO₃ (25 ml) solution, extracted with ether (3 × 30 ml), the ether extract dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated to yield unreacted chalcones, usually present in negligible

amount. The aqueous layer after concentration was acidified with dilute HCl and extracted with ether (4 × 25 ml). The ether extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and the solvent removed to yield the product. The products (**1a**, **2a**, **3a**) were crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and alcohol and were identified by their physicochemical properties (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.D.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. J. M. McCORD and I. FRIDOVICH, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 6049.
2. W. C. DANEN and R. J. WARNER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, **18**, 989.
3. D. T. SAWYER, M. J. GIBIAN, M. M. MORRISON and E. T. SEO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 627.
4. J. M. GEBICKI and B. H. J. BIELSKI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **103**, 7020.
5. K. BOUJLEL and J. SIMONET, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, **20**, 1063.
6. E. J. NANNI, JR., M. D. STALLINGS and D. T. SAWYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 4481.
7. I. ROSENTHAL and A. FRIMER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1976, **32**, 2805.
8. M. SINGH, K. N. SINGH and R. A. MISRA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1991, **64**, 2599.
9. M. SUGAWARA and M. M. BAIZER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 4931; H. YAMAMOTO, T. MASHINO, T. NAGANO and M. HIROBE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 4133; F. OJIMA, N. KOBAYASHI and T. OSA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1990 **63**, 1374; T. NAGANO, H. YAMAMOTO and M. HIROBE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 3529.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry". ELBS, London, 1978.
11. I. FRIDOVICH in "Molecular Mechanism of Oxygen Activation". ed. O. HAYAISHI, Academic, New York, 1974.